

Complex Compounds of Iridium. Part III. Compounds with Ammonia and Ethylamine.

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By the action of pyridine on $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (*cis*) two compounds $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{Py}$ and $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{Py}$ have been obtained; the remaining diethyl sulphide molecule could not be replaced by pyridine even when the reactants were heated in a sealed tube for 10 hours at $140^\circ\text{-}50^\circ$ (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 276). Prolonged heating even at much higher temperature (180°) did not yield better results. The substitution of ethylamine, however, in place of pyridine gives rise to three compounds, *viz.*, (I) $(\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{EtNH}_2)$, (II) $(\text{IrCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{EtNH}_2)\text{Cl}$ and (III) $(\text{IrCl} \cdot 5\text{EtNH}_2)\text{Cl}_2$, none of which contains diethyl sulphide although this reaction has been carried out at $130^\circ\text{-}135^\circ$ for 3 hours only. If $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ in benzene be refluxed with alcoholic ethylamine for 30 hours, a very minute quantity of a greenish yellow substance (m.p. 310° decomp.) soluble in water, is obtained and the rest becomes tarry. When ammonia is passed in the benzene or acetone solution no replacement of the sulphide molecule takes place but at 54° on prolonged action, a minute quantity of a substance, insoluble in benzene, unlike the parent body but containing nitrogen, is obtained. In a sealed tube at $140^\circ\text{-}145^\circ$, two compounds (IV) $(\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3)$ and (V) $(\text{IrCl} \cdot 5\text{NH}_3)\text{Cl}_2$ have been isolated. Palmaer, (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1895, 10, 320; 1897, 13, 211) obtained compound (V) from iridium trichloride hydrate and ammonia with much difficulty as it is not so easy to have the pure compound free from traces of ammonium chloride which invariably forms a part in Palmaer's method. At a still higher temperature, the yield of the compound (V) increases with the corresponding decrease of (IV) and a mixture is obtained which is soluble in cold water and contains iridium and chlorine almost in the invariable ratio of 1:3 and nitrogen. In both the cases there remains light yellow filtrate forming a glass like mass in vacuum, very hygroscopic

and containing sulphur and nitrogen. The complete or partial replacement of diethyl sulphide by ethylamine, ammonia, and pyridine, therefore, appears to depend more upon the strength of the bases concerned than on the temperature of the reaction.

The compounds (I—III) are stable, Werner complexes, (II) and (III) giving precipitates with an aqueous silver nitrate. The molecular conductivity of (III) at infinite dilution is 226 which is slightly lower than that of a ternary electrolyte. This may be due to a decreased mobility of the radicle ($\text{IrCl}\cdot 5\text{Et NH}_2$).

The compounds (IV) and (V) are less stable than the others in aqueous solution, both of them give precipitates with aqueous silver nitrate although all the chlorine atoms are supposed to be within the co-ordination group in (IV), *e.g.*

Its solution in water is not acidic, which precludes the possibility of the replacement of chlorine atoms by OH groups and consequent formation of HCl. The only possibility, therefore, is the formation of an aqueo compound which is very common in the ammino compounds of iridium. Moreover, the molecular conductivity of (V) indicates that all the three chlorine atoms ionise in solution to produce ($\text{Ir}\cdot 5\text{NH}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$) Cl_3 (*cf.* Lamb and Fairhall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 378).

Like most of the iridium ammines compounds (II) and (III), when treated with freshly prepared moist silver oxide, yield strongly basic solutions of light yellow colour. These compounds are strongly alkaline to litmus, liberate ammonia from ammonium salts when gently heated, and absorb carbon dioxide when exposed to the atmosphere; but on standing over silver oxide for 20 hours slowly they turn blue. On acidification of this blue solution, a dark blue precipitate, which may be iridium oxide or hydroxide, is obtained. Iridium chloropentammine chloride yields a stronger and more stable base (Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 34). The compound (IV) too, on similar treatment yields a strong base and it is more stable than those derived from compounds (II) and (III) as it does not decompose on standing. It partially precipitates silver hydroxide from aqueous silver nitrate and liberates ammonia from ammonium chloride when gently warmed.

The isolation of different salts of these bases will form the subject of our next communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{EtNH}_2$, $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{EtNH}_2$ and $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{EtNH}_2$.— $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (2.8 g.) and ethylamine (5 c.c. of 50% alcoholic solution) were heated in a sealed tube for 3 hours at 140° - 145° . The whole mass solidified on cooling and to this alcohol was added (A). The insoluble solid was separated, and was then extracted thrice with boiling water, first time the extraction being continued for 3 hours and 1 hour each for the successive ones. The insoluble substance was then washed with alcohol and ether, m.p. 220° (decomp.), light yellow substance. (Found: N, 9.61; Cl, 24.44; Ir, 44.17. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ requires N, 9.66; Cl, 24.4; Ir, 44.3 per cent). The aqueous solution was evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and was thrice recrystallised from hot water. It is sparingly soluble in cold water but readily so when warm, light yellow cubical plates, m.p. 281° - 82° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.56; Cl, 21.86; Ir, 40.06. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ requires N, 11.66; Cl, 22.1; Ir, 40.22 per cent). To the alcoholic mother liquor (A) ether was added with the separation of an oily substance. This oily substance was dissolved in acetone when a white substance was left behind. This substance was crystallised from water. It gradually decomposes without definite melting point when heated. The acetone solution on spontaneous evaporation yielded the same substance when it was left for 7 days but an oily substance still remained uncrystallised. It is soluble in cold water and when crystallised, it is of very light yellow colour. (Found: N, 12.85; Cl, 20.14; Ir, 36.87. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$ requires N, 13.2; Cl, 20.35; Ir, 36.76 per cent).

The molar conductivity of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{EtNH}_2$ at different concentrations in water at 29° ,

Molar conc.	...	0.001719	0.0008595	0.0004298
Molar conductivity	...	210.4	216.9	226.6

Preparation of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ and $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$.— $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (2.5 g.) and liquor ammonia (18 c.c. Merck) in a sealed tube were heated for 6 hours at 135° - 145° . When cold a white crystalline substance separated out and a yellow solution with a layer of

diethyl sulphide floating over it was obtained. The sulphide was extracted with ether; the main solution when concentrated over sulphuric acid yielded a light yellow crystalline substance. It is very soluble in water and does not melt when heated but gradually decomposes. It was crystallised twice from a mixture of acetone and water. It precipitates silver chloride from silver nitrate solution. (Found: N, 6.58; Cl, 25.0; S, 7.64; Ir, 45.6. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot 2\text{NH}_3$ requires N, 6.6; Cl, 25.1; S, 7.56; Ir 45.57 per cent). The filtrate from the above could not be crystallised. It is hygroscopic and contains NH_3 and Cl.

The insoluble white substance referred to above was thrice crystallised from boiling water. (Found: N, 18.4; Cl, 27.75; Ir, 50.0. $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 5\text{NH}_3$ requires N, 18.2; Cl, 27.69; Ir, 50.18 per cent.).

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